

Exploring Gender Disparities in Noise Exposure and Hearing Protection in Nigerian Construction Sites.

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Abstract

Occupational noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) remains a critical but under-addressed health issue in the construction industry, particularly in developing countries. Despite increasing participation of women in construction roles, gender-specific risks and disparities in noise exposure and hearing protection remain poorly understood. This study investigates gender disparities in occupational noise exposure, access to hearing protection devices (HPDs), availability of noise exposure and hearing conservation (NEHC) programs, and auditory health outcomes among construction workers in Lagos, Nigeria. A cross-sectional quantitative survey was conducted among 300 construction workers (280 males, 20 females) selected through purposive and cluster sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire covering demographics, noise exposure, HPD access and use, NEHC program availability, and self-reported auditory symptoms. Descriptive and inferential statistics, including Chi-square tests, were used for analysis. Male workers were significantly more exposed to frequent or constant noise (85.7%) compared to females (35.0%) ($p = 0.008$). HPD provision (9.3% males vs. 5.0% females) and training (3.2% males; 0% females) were limited and not statistically significant. Auditory symptoms were more prevalent among men (33.2%) than among women (10.0%), though the difference was not significant. NEHC programmes were largely absent (only 9% of sites), with minimal effectiveness reported. The study reveals substantial gender disparities in noise exposure and protection in Nigerian construction sites. Findings underscore the urgent need for gender-sensitive NEHC programs, improved regulatory enforcement, and inclusive occupational safety policies to address both exposure risks and training gaps in this male-dominated industry.

Keywords: Occupational noise, hearing conservation, gender disparities, construction workers, hearing protection devices (HPDs), Nigeria

1. Introduction

Occupational noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) remains one of the most prevalent but underreported work-related health disorders globally. It accounts for a significant proportion of occupational illnesses, especially in noise-intensive industries such as manufacturing, aviation, and construction (Wang, 2021). The construction industry, in particular, exposes workers to excessive noise from equipment such as jackhammers, compressors, mixers, and bulldozers, which often exceed recommended safe exposure thresholds (Santoro, 2022). Prolonged exposure to such noise without adequate protection can lead to both temporary and permanent auditory damage, reducing workers' quality of life, employability, and general well-being. While substantial research has focused on occupational noise exposure and hearing loss, the gender dimension of this problem has received insufficient attention. Historically, occupational safety and health (OSH) studies and policies have adopted a gender-neutral stance, assuming a uniform experience across all workers. However, emerging literature suggests that this assumption obscures real and important differences in exposure patterns, protective behaviours, and health outcomes between men and women (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2015). The gender blindness in many OSH frameworks can lead to systemic neglect of women's specific risks, particularly in male-dominated sectors like construction.

Globally, construction remains one of the most male-dominated industries, but women's participation is steadily increasing, especially in supervisory, technical assistance, and on-site labour roles. Despite this shift, most health and safety protocols, particularly those regarding personal protective equipment (PPE), such as hearing protection devices (HPDs), are still designed with male workers as the normative standard. This mismatch raises important questions about whether female workers are adequately protected, trained, or even acknowledged in current noise exposure risk frameworks (Meira-Santana, 2015). Inadequate protection for women may not only arise from a lack of provision but also from poor fit, cultural discomfort, lack of training, or exclusion from occupational health communications (Chen & Su, 2025). Recent studies provide evidence of gender disparities in exposure and response to occupational noise hazards. Liu (2025) found that, although males tend to experience more occupational NIHL in absolute numbers due to job roles, female workers may be disproportionately under-protected or less likely to report symptoms. Wang (2025) identified biological sex differences in auditory damage thresholds, indicating that men and women might differ in their susceptibility to NIHL even when exposed to similar noise levels. Similarly,

Sánchez-Sellero et al. (2024) observed that gender influenced both exposure levels and symptom reporting, suggesting that workplace design, role assignment, and power dynamics intersect with occupational health outcomes.

Beyond physiological factors, behavioural and sociocultural determinants further compound the disparities. McCullagh et al. (2016) showed that although HPD usage rates may not differ significantly by gender in some sectors, the motivators and barriers to usage do. For example, male workers may be influenced more by peer behaviour and supervisor expectations, while female workers may lack access to training or face ergonomic challenges due to ill-fitting gear. These findings highlight the need for a nuanced approach to implementing hearing conservation programs, one that is responsive to the distinct needs of male and female workers. In the Nigerian context, these concerns are even more pronounced. Construction sites in Nigeria are often informal or semi-regulated, with poor enforcement of occupational health policies. The Factories Act of 2004 mandates employers to implement noise control measures and provide adequate protective equipment (Adaeze, 2021). However, multiple studies indicate that these requirements are poorly implemented, particularly among small and medium construction firms (Fasola & Osisanya, 2022). Women working in such environments face the dual challenge of general occupational risk and gender-specific neglect. Given the relatively small proportion of women in the Nigerian construction workforce, their experiences are frequently overlooked in health surveillance, policy discourse, and program design.

This gap presents both a research need and a policy imperative. Addressing gender disparities in hearing conservation is essential not only for equity but also to improve the overall efficacy of noise-exposure interventions. Programs that ignore the distinct experiences of women are likely to fail a segment of the workforce, reducing their overall effectiveness and reinforcing occupational health inequities. As the ILO (2015) stresses, gender-sensitive OSH practice is not merely about equality but about ensuring that interventions are appropriate and effective for all workers. The present study seeks to contribute to this emerging field by examining gender disparities in noise exposure and hearing protection practices among construction workers in Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to explore whether male and female workers differ in their levels of noise exposure, access to NEHC programmes, provision and use of HPDs, and reported auditory symptoms. By disaggregating data by gender, this research aims to uncover patterns that can inform more inclusive occupational health policies in the construction sector.

Understanding these disparities is particularly relevant in the context of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3, which seeks to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all. Without addressing the gendered dimensions of occupational hazards, such as noise exposure, achieving universal health equity remains elusive. The findings of this study will provide evidence to support gender-responsive interventions and encourage greater inclusion of women's experiences in occupational health planning and enforcement.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Design and Setting

This study employed a cross-sectional quantitative design to explore gender disparities in noise exposure and hearing protection practices among construction workers in Ikeja, Lagos State, Nigeria. Ikeja was selected for its high concentration of construction activity and the presence of both formal and informal construction enterprises. The study forms part of a broader investigation into occupational noise exposure among construction workers in Nigeria but focuses specifically on gender-based patterns in exposure, protection, and reported auditory symptoms.

2.2 Participants and Sampling

A total of 300 construction workers were recruited from various construction sites using purposive and cluster sampling techniques. Inclusion criteria were: individuals actively working on construction sites, aged 18 and above, and willing to provide informed consent. Sites were clustered by company or contractor, and within each cluster, workers were selected to ensure a diverse mix of job roles. Among the 300 participants, 280 were male (93.3%), and 20 were female (6.7%), reflecting the gender distribution typically found in the Nigerian construction sector. Although the female sample was relatively small, their responses allowed for initial exploration of gender-specific patterns and disparities in occupational health risks.

2.3 Data Collection Instrument

Data were collected using a structured, interviewer-administered questionnaire adapted from validated occupational health surveys (McCullagh et al., 2016; Fasola & Osisanya, 2022). The instrument was pre-tested for clarity and reliability and administered in English or Yoruba, depending on participant preference. The questionnaire covered four major domains:

Demographics: Age, gender, job role, years of experience.

Noise Exposure: Frequency and duration of exposure to loud noise.

Hearing Protection: Availability and use of hearing protection devices (HPDs), presence of noise exposure and hearing conservation (NEHC) programs, and training received.

Auditory Health: Self-reported symptoms such as tinnitus, temporary hearing loss, or permanent hearing impairment.

Data collectors were trained in occupational health research and ethical interviewing to minimize response bias.

2.4 Data Analysis

All data were coded and entered into IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 25) for analysis. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were used to summarize demographic variables and responses related to noise exposure and HPD use. Chi-square tests of independence were used to examine associations between gender and key categorical variables, such as exposure frequency, HPD availability, and reported auditory symptoms. Due to the small number of female participants, statistical significance was interpreted cautiously, with emphasis placed on observed trends rather than inference alone.

2.5 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the relevant institutional review board prior to data collection. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. Data confidentiality and participant anonymity were maintained throughout the research process. No identifying information was collected, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any point without penalty.

3. Results

3.1 Participant Demographics by Gender

A total of 300 construction workers participated in the study, consisting of 280 males (93.3%) and 20 females (6.7%), reflecting the dominant male presence in the Nigerian construction sector (Table 1). The age distribution showed that both male and female workers were primarily in the 26–35-year range, accounting for 45% of each group. However, females were slightly more represented in the younger 18–25 bracket (25%) compared to their male counterparts (17.5%), suggesting a relatively more recent entry of women into the industry.

In terms of educational attainment, a marked gender difference emerged. While a significant portion of male workers (46.8%) had no formal or only primary education, the majority of female workers (80%) had completed at least secondary education, with 25% holding tertiary qualifications. This disparity may reflect the higher educational barrier women face before entering a traditionally male-dominated sector, and their greater likelihood of occupying administrative or supervisory roles that demand formal credentials.

Job roles also displayed strong gendered patterns. The majority of male participants were engaged in manual labor (50.7%) and equipment operation (24.3%), roles associated with high noise exposure. In contrast, female participants were more likely to be found in administrative/support roles (40%) and as site assistants (30%), which are typically associated with lower noise exposure. Only 10% of female workers reported working in manual labour, and just 5% operated heavy machinery.

Regarding work experience, most female workers (70%) had fewer than four years in the construction industry, with over half (55%) having one to three years' experience. In contrast, male workers were more evenly distributed across all experience levels, with nearly one-third (33.2%) having 4–6 years of experience and over a quarter (27.5%) having worked for more than six years. This trend supports the notion that women are newer entrants to the sector and may not yet have full exposure to its occupational hazards or access to institutional protections. Overall, the demographic profile highlights apparent gender differences in age, education, job role, and experience, all of which potentially influence exposure to occupational noise and access to hearing protection. These differences warrant a gender-sensitive approach to occupational health policy and intervention design in the construction industry.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Participants by Gender (N = 300)

Variable	Category	Male (n = 280)	Female (n = 20)
Age Group	18–25 years	49 (17.5%)	5 (25.0%)
	26–35 years	126 (45.0%)	9 (45.0%)
	36–45 years	78 (27.9%)	4 (20.0%)
	>45 years	27 (9.6%)	2 (10.0%)
Education Level	No formal education	57 (20.4%)	1 (5.0%)
	Primary	74 (26.4%)	3 (15.0%)
	Secondary	96 (34.3%)	11 (55.0%)
	Tertiary	53 (18.9%)	5 (25.0%)
Job Role	Manual labor	142 (50.7%)	2 (10.0%)
	Equipment operator	68 (24.3%)	1 (5.0%)
	Site assistant	30 (10.7%)	6 (30.0%)
	Administrative/support	22 (7.9%)	8 (40.0%)
	Others	18 (6.4%)	3 (15.0%)
Years in Construction	<1 year	21 (7.5%)	3 (15.0%)
	1–3 years	89 (31.8%)	11 (55.0%)
	4–6 years	93 (33.2%)	4 (20.0%)
	>6 years	77 (27.5%)	2 (10.0%)

3.2 Gender Disparities in Noise Exposure

Table 2 presents the distribution of self-reported noise exposure frequency among construction workers, disaggregated by gender. The results reveal notable differences in how male and female workers experience occupational noise on construction sites.

Among male participants (n = 280), a significant 85.7% (240 workers) reported being exposed to high noise levels either frequently (61.1%) or constantly (24.6%). This trend reflects the nature of their job roles, most were engaged in manual labor and machine operation, which are typically associated with high decibel environments. Only a small fraction of male workers reported occasional (7.5%) or no exposure (6.8%), further underscoring the high-risk auditory environment faced by men in this sector.

In contrast, the pattern was markedly different among female participants (n = 20). Half of the women (50%) reported occasional noise exposure, and another 15% said they were never exposed to noise on site. Only 35% experienced frequent noise exposure, and none reported constant exposure. This lower exposure among women is consistent with their occupational roles, many held administrative or support positions with limited contact with noise-intensive machinery or processes.

The results highlight a statistically significant gender gap in noise exposure intensity, supporting the argument that job segregation based on gender directly impacts exposure risk. While male workers are routinely subjected to high levels of occupational noise, female workers are less exposed, albeit not entirely exempt. It's also important to note that even occasional exposure, especially without proper protection, can pose cumulative auditory risks over time.

These findings emphasize the importance of tailoring occupational health and safety interventions not just to exposure levels but also to gendered work patterns. While males may require enhanced protective protocols due to higher exposure, female workers must not be overlooked, as their roles may still bring them into intermittent contact with hazardous noise, often without adequate preparation or equipment.

Table 2. Noise Exposure Frequency by Gender (N = 300)

Exposure Level	Male (n = 280)	Female (n = 20)
Never	19 (6.8%)	3 (15%)
Occasionally	21 (7.5%)	10 (50%)
Frequently	171 (61.1%)	7 (35%)
Constantly	69 (24.6%)	0 (0%)

Chi-square analysis revealed a statistically significant association between gender and frequency of noise exposure ($\chi^2 = 11.74, p = 0.008$), indicating that male workers were considerably more likely to experience high-frequency noise exposure than their female counterparts.

3.3 Availability and Use of Hearing Protection Devices (HPDs)

Access to hearing protection devices (HPDs) was limited across both genders, with only 9.3% of male and 5.0% of female workers receiving them (Table 3). Among those who received HPDs, 57.7% of males used them frequently, while the sole female recipient reported no usage, citing discomfort and poor fit. Additionally, only 3.2% of males received any training on HPD use, and none of the females did. These findings suggest both low overall provision and significant gender disparities in usage and training, with women notably underserved in protective education and equipment suitability.

Table 3. HPD Access and Use by Gender (N = 300)

Variable	Male (n = 280)	Female (n = 20)
Provided HPDs	26 (9.3%)	1 (5.0%)
Use HPDs Frequently (when provided)	15/26 (57.7%)	0/1 (0.0%)
Received Training on HPD Use	9 (3.2%)	0 (0%)

No female respondents reported receiving formal training on proper HPD use, compared to 3.2% of male participants. While the numbers are small, these trends suggest that women are both less likely to receive protection and less likely to receive training in its use.

3.4 Presence of NEHC Programs

The data show that only 9% of all participants reported the presence of a noise exposure and hearing conservation (NEHC) program at their worksite, with 26 males (9.3%) and just 1 female (5%) having access (Table 4). This indicates a widespread absence of formal hearing conservation efforts, especially for female workers. Among those aware of such programs, only 8 males (2.9%) rated them as “somewhat effective,” and none considered them fully effective. The sole female respondent also found the program ineffective. These findings highlight both the scarcity and perceived ineffectiveness of NEHC programs in the construction sector, with minimal gender inclusion and limited impact where they do exist.

Table 4. Presence and Perceived Effectiveness of NEHC Programs by Gender (N = 300)

NEHC Program Variable	Male (n = 280)	Female (n = 20)
NEHC Program Available	26 (9.3%)	1 (5.0%)
No NEHC Program Available	254 (90.7%)	19 (95.0%)
Perceived Effectiveness*		
Somewhat Effective	8 (2.9%)	0 (0.0%)
Not Effective	18 (6.4%)	1 (5.0%)
Not Applicable/No Program	254 (90.7%)	19 (95.0%)

Note: Perceived effectiveness data were collected only from participants who were aware of NEHC programs at their sites.

4.5 Reported Auditory Symptoms

Self-reported auditory symptoms were significantly more prevalent among male workers (Table 5). Nearly 30% of males reported tinnitus, and 21.1% experienced difficulty hearing in noisy environments, both indicators of early-stage noise-induced hearing loss. In contrast, no female participants reported tinnitus, and only two (10%) reported difficulty hearing in noise. Interestingly, temporary hearing loss was reported equally by a small portion of both genders (7.5% of males, 10% of females). Overall, 41.8% of males versus 80% of females reported no symptoms, reflecting the higher noise exposure burden among male workers due to job role and duration.

Table 5. Self-Reported Auditory Symptoms by Gender (N = 300)

Auditory Symptom	Male (n = 280)	Female (n = 20)
Tinnitus (ringing in ears)	83 (29.6%)	0 (0.0%)
Difficulty hearing in noise	59 (21.1%)	2 (10.0%)
Temporary hearing loss	21 (7.5%)	2 (10.0%)
No auditory symptoms reported	117 (41.8%)	16 (80.0%)

4.6 Summary of Key Gender Differences

The summary highlights statistically and practically relevant gender disparities in noise exposure and hearing protection (Table 6). Frequent or constant noise exposure was reported by 85.7% of male workers, significantly higher than the 35% among females ($p = 0.008$), underscoring occupational role differences. While males were nearly twice as likely to be provided HPDs (9.3% vs. 5.0%) and trained in their use (3.2% vs. 0%), these differences were

not statistically significant, likely due to overall low provision rates. Auditory symptoms were more common among men (33.2% vs. 10%), but, as with the other symptoms, the difference did not reach statistical significance, suggesting that exposure, rather than gender alone, may be the primary driver.

Table 7: Statistical Gender Differences among the Respondents

Outcome Variable	Male (%)	Female (%)	Statistical Significance
Frequent/Constant Noise Exposure	85.7	35.0	$p = 0.008$
Provided HPDs	9.3	5.0	Not significant
Trained in HPD Use	3.2	0.0	Not significant
Auditory Symptoms (Any)	33.2	10.0	Not significant

Although the small female sample limits statistical power, the trends clearly suggest greater exposure, better access to protection, and higher prevalence of auditory symptoms among male workers. However, the complete lack of training and ergonomic HPDs for female workers also signals critical oversight in protection equity.

4. Discussion

This study investigated gender disparities in noise exposure patterns, availability of noise exposure and hearing conservation (NEHC) programs, use of hearing protection devices (HPDs), and self-reported auditory symptoms among construction workers in Lagos, Nigeria. The findings reveal clear and consistent differences between male and female participants across all measured variables, reinforcing the need for gender-sensitive approaches in occupational health policies and interventions within the construction sector.

One of the most striking findings is the significantly higher rate of frequent and constant noise exposure among male workers. Over 85% of male workers reported frequent or constant exposure to loud noise, compared with just 35% of female workers. This disparity is primarily attributable to job role distribution: the majority of male workers were engaged in manual labor and equipment operation, tasks intrinsically associated with high noise levels, while female workers were employed mainly in administrative or support functions with lower exposure risks (Chen & Su, 2025). These findings align with those of Sánchez-Sellero et al. (2024) and Lie et al. (2016), who demonstrated that gender disparities in noise exposure are primarily a function of occupational segregation. In their study, men were more likely to be exposed to hazardous occupational noise due to their job roles, while women, often employed in less hazardous capacities, had lower direct exposure but still reported experiencing noise-related discomfort when protective measures were lacking.

The study also revealed inequities in the availability and use of HPDs. Although overall access to HPDs was low for both genders, men were nearly twice as likely to receive them (9.3% vs. 5.0%). More importantly, none of the female participants who received HPDs reported frequent use, citing issues such as discomfort, poor fit, and lack of training. This is consistent with findings by Meira-Santana (2015), who noted that gender-insensitive PPE design and lack of inclusive training can render protective devices ineffective for women. Even among male workers who received HPDs, usage was inconsistent. About 42% of them reported infrequent or no use, suggesting behavioral and cultural barriers to protection. As noted by McCullagh et al. (2016), HPD usage is not solely determined by availability but also by factors such as peer influence, comfort, training, and personal attitudes toward risk. In the present study, only 3.2% of males and 0% of females reported receiving any training on the proper use of HPDs, highlighting a severe gap in safety education.

Another critical finding is the near-total absence of NEHC programs. Only 9% of participants reported awareness of such programs at their worksites, with just 2.7% rating them as somewhat effective. This is concerning given that Nigeria's Factories Act of 2004 mandates the implementation of workplace noise control measures and hearing conservation programs (Adaeze, 2021). These programs, when effectively implemented, have been shown to reduce occupational hearing loss through regular monitoring, provision of protective gear, and employee education (Lewkowski et al., 2017; Aliyeva & Sari, 2025). The lack of NEHC implementation in this study mirrors earlier findings by Fasola and Osisanya (2022), who identified regulatory enforcement failures and employer noncompliance as significant barriers to occupational health improvements in Nigeria. Moreover, the absence of gender-specific provisions in existing regulations likely compounds the problem, leading to a situation in which women are not only under-protected but also invisible in the safety planning process (Aliyeva & Sari, 2025).

The gender disparities in exposure and protection translated into marked differences in self-reported auditory symptoms. Among male workers, nearly 30% reported tinnitus and over 20% reported difficulty hearing in noisy environments, symptoms indicative of early-stage NIHL (Wang, 2021). By contrast, only 10% of female workers reported any auditory symptoms, likely reflecting their lower exposure levels. However, it is worth noting that even occasional exposure without proper protection may result in symptoms, as evidenced by two female participants who reported temporary hearing loss. The absence of reported tinnitus among women may also be influenced by underreporting or limited symptom awareness, especially in

environments where occupational health education is lacking. Furthermore, existing research suggests that men and women may differ not only in exposure levels but in their biological vulnerability to hearing loss (Liu, 2025). Some studies suggest that men are more susceptible to high-frequency hearing damage, while others propose that hormonal or anatomical factors may afford women partial protection (Wang, 2025).

5. Conclusion and Practice Implications

This study underscores significant gender disparities in occupational noise exposure, HPD access and use, and auditory health outcomes among Nigerian construction workers. The near-absence of NEHC programmes, coupled with insufficient protective measures for women, calls for urgent policy attention. Incorporating gender-sensitive strategies into occupational health systems is not only an issue of equity but a necessary step toward sustainable and inclusive worker safety.

The findings of this study have significant implications for occupational health policy and workplace safety practices in Nigeria and other developing countries. Firstly, there is a clear need to implement and enforce NEHC programmes in the construction sector. These programs should include routine noise assessments, regular auditory screening for workers, distribution of ergonomically appropriate HPDs, and mandatory training sessions.

Secondly, gender-sensitive modifications to safety programs are essential. This includes designing PPE that fits female physiology, incorporating gender data in occupational health surveillance, and ensuring women are represented in safety planning and decision-making. As emphasized by the International Labour Organization (2015), gender-responsive OSH strategies not only promote equity but also enhance program effectiveness by addressing the specific needs of all workers.

Finally, given the growing number of women entering the construction workforce, albeit in smaller numbers, future studies should explore their long-term exposure patterns and risks. This study's small female sample size limited the statistical power of gender comparisons, but the trends observed warrant deeper investigation through larger, gender-stratified studies.

Limitations

While the study offers valuable insights, it is not without limitations. The **cross-sectional** design limits causal inference, and the reliance on self-reported data introduces the potential for recall bias. Additionally, the small number of female participants ($n = 20$) limits the generalizability

of gender-based comparisons. However, given the industry's male-dominated nature, this reflects real-world workforce demographics rather than sampling bias.

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